

IMPORTANCE OF CLASS-MANAGE FOR MORE PRODUCTIVE AND HEALTHFUL LESSONS. HOW TO ORGANIZE MOVABLE CLASSES: TIPS AND BENEFITS.

Khakimova Dilshoda Oybek qizi

Faculty of English philology and teaching, Uzbekistan State World Languages University, Tashkent, Uzbekistan

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Abstract. *The article sheds light on information, methods and tips about how to manage a class and organize movable classes by providing clear examples and movement activities.*

Key words: *movable class, prolonged sitting, standing, sedentary behavior, traditional class, walking, movement, stand-ups, breaks, team-building, timer, physical activity, games, Australian Health Survey, flexible design.*

ВАЖНОСТЬ УПРАВЛЕНИЯ КЛАССОМ ДЛЯ БОЛЕЕ ПРОДУКТИВНЫХ И ЗДОРОВЫХ УРОКОВ. КАК ОРГАНИЗОВАТЬ ПОДВИЖНЫЕ КЛАССЫ: СОВЕТЫ И ПРЕИМУЩЕСТВА.

Аннотация. *Статья дает информацию, методы и советы о том, как управлять классом и организовывать подвижные классы, предоставляя четкие примеры и двигательные действия.*

Ключевые слова: *подвижный класс, длительное сидение, стояние, малоподвижное поведение, традиционный класс, ходьба, движение, стоячие места, перерывы, тимбилдинг, таймер, физическая активность, игры, Австралийское Обследование Здоровья, гибкий дизайн.*

INTRODUCTION

Furniture, desks and chairs are the main types of equipment in a class throughout the world. In today's fast-changing globe, a lot of pupils and students spend their time on sitting in the classrooms and having classes, clearly, they are used to live in a sedentary life. People around the world are suffering from many health and social troubles, and obesity rates among adults but also children brings on a global health hazard. Steps to reduce obesity among children tend to focus on healthier eating and more exercise, but cutting down on sedentary behavior (SB), like "screen time" or simply sitting on the bus or in school, needs to be a heated topic of controversy as well. Since children spend a significant amount of time in school, making changes there to lower sedentary time can offer health benefits on its own, as well as help to make a great progress in terms of educational growth.

As it is clear from informative news in authentic sources that almost every educational place of developing countries has a standard way of equipping the classrooms, however, some teachers are fortunate that their classrooms have hybrid desk-chairs that can be moved anytime. But even these types of desks and chairs are often arranged in rows and they remain the same. Around much of the globe, classroom desks are heavy: bolted to the floor and shared by three or four students. At universities and institutions, lecturers face auditoriums with connected rows and immovable seats.

The first environment in which an individual is exposed to much sitting is the school environment. In 1981, Mandal renamed modern humans "homo sedens" owing to the many

hours spent in a sitting position from childhood up to now[1]. In school, students learn and acquire the basement of knowledge they will maintain throughout their lives, so students should be educated about the negative consequences of long hours of sitting and sedentary behavior, such as unfavorable body composition, decreased fitness, less scores for self-esteem, and decreased academic achievement, and should learn practical strategies to escape from these negative effects above. Traditional classroom designs offer a clear message that ‘ Students should sit and listen what his teacher is saying’[2]. But today’s modern research tells a different way of teaching. As the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (2010, 6) informs, ‘ found a positive associations between classroom- based physical activity and indicators of cognitive skills and attitudes, academic behavior and academic achievement’[8].

To begin with, let’s compare the differences between a movable class and a traditional class.

<i>MOVABLE CLASS</i>	<i>TRADITIONAL CLASS</i>
Getting out of seats at least once per hour	Especially higher level students sit throughout the entire lesson
Tasks with movements and actions during activities	Movement of students are referred as a bad behavior
Desk-based activities in pair work or group work format	Almost all activities are desk-based
Teachers, students both are ready to reconfigure desks and chairs	Teacher does not do some changes to make a lively and energetic atmosphere

Think back to when you were small, you swang your legs when you were sitting in a chair. From the perspective of teachers and tutors of yours, doing so was your fault and result of bad behavior. No! It was okay and stop feeling guilty for those kind of action you did in school times. M. Montessori told us in her book named ‘The Secret of Childhood’, ‘ Movement or physical activity is an essential factor of intellectual growth’[3]. One of the leading philosopher Friedrich Nietzsche said that ‘ All great ideas are conceived by walking’[4]. Now there is an evidence that the human brain is designed to think while moving’. From my own experience, I can say that my brain can memorize what I read while walking like facts, poems and etc.

Now we can understand that English or any kind of teachers from various subjects cannot bring swimming, volleyball or wood chopping into classroom. However, this can be accomplished by adding simple standing activities or Fast Action Breaks that are easy and fun by working for all ages and levels.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Sitting Too Much Hurts

Physical inactivity contributes to over three million preventable deaths worldwide each year. It is the fourth leading cause of death due to non-communicable diseases.

It’s also the cause of 21–25 per cent of breast and colon cancers, 27 per cent of diabetes cases, and around 30 per cent of ischaemic heart disease. In fact, physical inactivity is the second highest cause of cancer in Australia, behind tobacco smoking.

The Australian Health Survey 2011–12 results show:

- 60 per cent of Australian adults do less than the recommended 30 minutes of moderate intensity physical activity each day.
- Only one third of Australian children, and one in 10 young people (aged 5–17), do the recommended 60 minutes of physical activity every day.
- Fewer than one in three children and young people have no more than two hours of screen time each day.
- Almost 70 per cent of Australian adults can be classed as either sedentary or having low levels of physical activity [5].

It is true that life span is longer now that it was in the past, but the causes of incurable diseases are different. For instance, diabetes, heart disease, some types of cancer, and dementia have been connected to extensive sitting. To break the sitting cycle, all we need is active stand-ups and exercises. Now some are can be exemplified.

Stand-up breaks

- Stand-up and stretch – shake your fingers, clasp your hands, lift your arms and take a few deep breath. Jog in if you feel comfortable.
- Phone check – students can be given 2-3 minutes to check their phones by standing out of their desks.
- Meet and greet – Students are given some minutes to go around the class and introduce themselves to someone they do not know, if they know each other already, discussion questions may be given.
- Standing answers – it is like a ‘*yes or no*’ questions, when a teacher gives a question, if students agree, they should stand up, if it is not, they must sit.

While doing actions above, using a timer is advisable in order to regulate the length of breaks [6].

Breaks with Fast Actions

Those types of actions require more action and even stupidity. If you use them during classes by chance, students may consider it like a way of wasting time, therefore, teachers should write them in their lesson plans as others see that Fast Action Breaks are preplanned and a part of the course.

Here are some ideas to practice:

Dance Break – try to move students with the songs like “Head, Shoulder, Knees and Toes”, “The Hokey Pokey”, “If You are Happy and You Know It, Clap Your Hands” or etc which allow you to do any movement.

Pantomime – Start a collection of movements on papers or small cards:

“Walk like a robot”.

“Swim like a horse”.

“Laugh like a dolphin.”

“Pretend you are eating pasta while standing on one leg”.

“Pretend you are having a meeting with the President and he gave you a luxurious apartment”.

Be sure that students fulfill the tasks by moving and acting. As soon as you finish the task, ask students to write their own Pantomime Tasks. Then collect these and put them in a box so that you will have a massive archive.

Find the Thing – Announce that you have lost your small items like a pen, a pencil, an eraser or a ring. Students rise from desks and start to search for the thing. In this case, the winner must be awarded! Of course, with NO CANDY! Try to stimulate them with certificates or educational tools. Moreover, during the task, it is necessary not to use hands while searching for something: students are not allowed to open bags, move desks or turn baskets upside-down. For this, the item must be visible[7].

Team-Building Activities

Team building brings people together by encouraging collaboration and teamwork.

Team building in the studying places is the process of creating a team that is cohesively working together towards a common goal. The main purpose of team building is to create a strong team through forming bonds and connections and achieving goals. Creating these bonds through team building is very beneficial to individuals, organizations. The benefits of team building include increased communication, planning skills, motivation, and student collaboration. Fun activities that help people see each other in a different role allow them to connect in a different setting. Team-building games and activities are a fun and wise way to help students learn to work together, listen attentively, communicate clearly, and think creatively. They also give students the chance to get to know each other, build trust as a community, create a friendly atmosphere. In the following, you can see some common types of team-building activities that you can put into practice while teaching:

1. Colored spots

For this activity, you will place a colored sticker dot on each student's forehead, without them knowing what color it is. When the game begins, each "team" of students (with the same color) must find each other—*without speaking or miming*. This task encourages non-verbal communication and cooperation.

2. Hot seat

This fun game is a lot like the game show *Password*. Split the class into two teams and have them sit together in teams facing the whiteboard or chalkboard. Then take an empty chair (one for each team) and put it at the front of the class, facing the team members. These chairs are the "hot seats". Choose one volunteer from each team to come up and sit in the "hot seat," facing their teammates with their back to the board. A list of vocabulary words to use for the game must be ready. Choose one and write it clearly on the board. Each team will take turns trying to get their teammate in the hot seat to guess the word, using synonyms, antonyms, definitions, etc. Make sure team members work together so that each member has a chance to provide information. The student in the hot seat listens to their teammates and tries to guess the word. The first hot seat student to say the word wins a point for their team. Once the word is successfully guessed, a new student from each team sits in the hot seat, and a new round begins with a different word.

3. Spider web

This team-building game will teach students that even though they may be different in many ways, they are still connected to one another. Gather in a circle, standing or sitting. (Standing is more comfortable and interesting). The game begins when the first person, holding a large ball of twine, tells the group a funny or embarrassing story about themselves. Once they finish, they will hold onto the end of the round and throw the ball to someone else in the circle.

That person grabs hold and tells a funny or embarrassing story about themselves and then passes it on to another student. Play continues until the twine has been passed to each person. The end result will produce a “spider web” out of the twine, connecting each student to all of the others.

You are a teacher and you should be more creative than you think. Bringing movement to traditional tasks helps you to incorporate more and more language practice into your movement activities. In this way, you do a great favor to students by simultaneously teaching a subject and contributing to their health [9].

RESULTS

Train and Move throughout the course

Training does not happen during only one lessons, it requires more practice and practice makes perfect. Do it regularly with students and gradually make them challenging so students can increase their group-making and team-building skills. Do not forget to choose meaningful and fun activities. And one more tip is that find a method to deal with even little stuff and usually associate these things (like books, lunches, phones, balls, balloons) with classroom management.

Movement matters in a child’s life during recess, physical education, and in their general education classroom. While children are getting activities throughout the day like physical education, it is not enough. Movement and physical activity allow students to do their best learning. In addition, many practitioners believe that the relationship between specific movements and developing neurons influence academic achievement. Brain research also finds a link between movement and the benefits it may have on a developing brain. When sensorimotor and cognitive processes work together, neurons in a child’s brain grow and meld with one another, making them quicker and better at sending and receiving messages. Fresh oxygen is also provided during periods of movements, allowing the brain to function at its best. When children are physically moving, their brains are creating neurological foundations that help to develop and foster creativity, problem solving, and language development. While brain research points to the benefits of using movement to strengthen the mind, lifestyle changes and legislature have affected how movement is viewed in the school setting. Movement can also help to lower anxiety, stress and depression as well as help to develop or boost a child’s self-esteem. Learning with and through movement can be a great place to start and teach students beneficial habits from early childhood on that will help carry them into their adult lives.

CONCLUSION

Let’s think about the future classroom. Bright and large classrooms with probably modern technologies: fast Internet, machine translators, 3D printers, mobile devices. One day those things and changes will absolutely happen. However, who will think about the physical space. I believe if we start to bring movement activities in classrooms. We will have more flexible design: movable and adjustable desks and chairs. It will be a large space to play student-to-student form of games. Nowadays, prolonged sitting is considered as one of the public health issues, and I see that movement during classes at educational places can do something to prevent the disease. Additionally, after reading the techniques, some teachers or students may feel strange or risky to have the methods of teaching calling them impossible. But as a student, I can say that standing lessons are more productive and full of energy, for my course mates feel free, energized and in the center of attention.

In the beginning, without practicing everything may seem too much difficult to deal with. There is a wise quote, “If there is no opportunity, create it! If there is not a door, just build it!” Sometimes when I enter a classroom, I see 20-30 pupils, and I think, huh! But after some seconds, I realize I will find a way, and start practicing sitting down and sitting up. Seemingly, after some minutes, we move!

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